

Leveraging Disease prevention and health promotion to control, prevent and respond to epidemics, communicable and non-communicable diseases - The role of Islamic principles, Teachings, and Practices.

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Abstract

In the recent past, the world has been hit by pandemics like coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), Monkey pox and epidemics like Ebola Virus Disease (EVD), as well as Marburg among others in different parts of the world. It has also been observed that employing public health measures specifically disease prevention and Health Promotion are fundamental pillars in preventing, controlling, and managing these global threats. Integrating religious teachings and practices, particularly Islamic principles, offers a culturally rooted and spiritually meaningful pathway to advancing these public health strategies. This paper explores and presents how Islamic teachings, principles, and practices—derived from the Qur'an and Sunnah—align with and enhance disease prevention and health promotion across primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. It also highlights practical health-related behaviours advocated for in Islam, including hygiene, nutrition, sexual conduct, and spiritual wellness, and their application in controlling preventing and responding to epidemics communicable and non-communicable diseases. A call to action is made for Muslim medical professionals to integrate Islamic teachings, guidance and practices into public health and medical teaching and practice in the training of health care professionals. More scientific research studies should be done to align prophetic medicine (Tibb a Nabbawi) with modern scientific medical knowledge. Further research should explore behavioural outcomes from faith-based health education programs and assess their effectiveness across populations.

Introduction

The globe has been hit by simultaneous episodes of epidemics and pandemics and pandemics in recent

decades. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), COVID-19 alone registered a total of more than 7 million deaths by December 2024 (1) and the accumulated number of cases by December 2024 was

778 million (2). The recent Monkey pox epidemic has so far claimed 328 deaths and the accumulated number of cases was 142,151 up to April 2025. (3,4). Ebola virus disease (EBV), Marburg, Cholera and other outbreaks have also hit different parts of the world in the recent past. (5,6) Islam is more than a religion—it is a comprehensive way and a complete system of life that encompasses guidance on spiritual, social, and physical well-being. (7,8) The intersection of Islamic principles and public health provides a potent framework for addressing the global burden of communicable and non-communicable diseases. By drawing on Islamic teachings, this paper aims to highlight how faith-informed strategies, Islamic teachings and practices can contribute to disease prevention and health promotion, preparedness and response to epidemics and pandemics as well as control and prevention of non-communicable diseases within our communities.

Background; definition of terms and sources of information.

Islam: Is the total submission to the will of Allah; It is a complete way of life; and it is the best way of life (9)

According to WHO, “**Health**” is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”. (WHO 1948) The WHO definition does not explain **the spiritual component of health**. (10)

Some researchers tend to describe **spiritual health** as a feeling of happiness and contentment. They do not differentiate between “**mental health**” and “**spiritual health**.” Islam emphasizes a fourth dimension: spiritual health, which encompasses moral clarity, inner peace, and devotion to divine guidance.

Mental health is "a state of emotional and psychological well-being in which an individual is able to use his or her cognitive and emotional capabilities, function in society, and meet the ordinary demands of everyday life." (11)

Spiritual health, on the contrary, means an individual's ability to differentiate between right and wrong and resolve to lead a more righteous life, free of stratagems, deception, dishonesty, and selfishness. Islam promotes the issue of spiritual health as well. (12,13)

The position of Islam and the Quran; “**Health** is a state of complete **physical, mental, spiritual and social wellbeing**, which must be safeguarded not only through

the maintenance of a health preserving regime at the **personal/individual** level, but also through the establishment of a health-protective and promoting **family system** and a health protective and **promoting social system**.” (14)

A disease, is any harmful deviation from the normal structural or functional state of an organism, generally associated with certain signs and symptoms and differing in nature from physical injury. A diseased organism commonly exhibits signs or symptoms indicative of its abnormal state. (15,16) For the purposes of this manuscript, we shall classify diseases into, Communicable and Non communicable diseases.

- 1. Communicable diseases:** These are diseases that can spread from one person to another through a variety of ways that include; contact with blood and bodily fluids; breathing in an airborne virus; or by being bitten by an insect. These diseases are usually caused by microorganisms including bacteria; viruses, parasites, among others. (17)
- 2. Non-Communicable diseases:** These are diseases that are not transmissible directly from one person to another. They may include but are not limited to cardiovascular diseases; cancers, diabetes, psychiatric and mental health diseases, among others.

This paper will discuss the Islamic aspects of disease prevention for both communicable and non-communicable diseases. (18)

Sources of Islamic teachings:

Islamic teachings are primarily derived from the Quran and Sunnah, which collectively form the basis of Shariah. The Quran and Sunnah make up Shariah (pathway), the source of all principles of Islamic law. (19,20) The sources of all knowledge and guidance to human kind and nature. The Quran is the words of Allah and the Sunnah are prophetic hadiths and traditions.

Secondary sources such as Qiyas (analogical reasoning) and Ijma' (consensus) support jurisprudence and health-related decision-making where explicit texts are absent. The concepts of qiyas and ijma' are used to legislate in the absence of rulings from the Quran and the Sunnah. For the purpose of this presentation, we shall stick to **Quran and Sunnah/hadith or prophetic traditions**. (21,22)

Disease prevention: This will be defined as specific, population-based, and individual-based interventions for primary and secondary (early detection) prevention, aiming to minimize the burden of diseases and associated risk factors. There are three levels of disease prevention including primary secondary and tertiary levels of diseases prevention.

Primary prevention aims to prevent disease or injury before it ever occurs. It includes actions aimed at avoiding the manifestation of a disease. This can be through;

- ❖ Changing the impact of social and economic determinants on health;
- ❖ Provision of information on behavioural and medical health risks.
- ❖ Nutritional and food supplementation;
- ❖ Oral and dental hygiene education;
- ❖ Clinical preventive services such as immunization and vaccination.
- ❖ Post-exposure prophylaxis for people exposed to a communicable disease.

Secondary prevention aims to reduce the impact of a disease or injury that has already occurred. This can be through

- ❖ Early screening and detection of a disease when this improves the chances of positive health outcomes of a particular disease.
- ❖ Detecting and treating disease or injury as soon as possible to halt or slow its progress,
- ❖ Regular exams and screening tests to detect disease in its earliest stages (e.g. mammograms to detect breast cancer)
- ❖ Daily, low-dose aspirins and/or diet and exercise programs to prevent further heart attacks or strokes.

Tertiary prevention: This aims to soften the impact of an ongoing illness or injury that has lasting effects. This can be achieved through the following measures among others;

- ❖ Through helping people to manage long-term, often-complex health problems and injuries.
- ❖ Vocational rehabilitation programs to retrain workers for new jobs when they have recovered as much as possible.

On disease prevention the prophet had this to say in a hadith in *Shahih Bukhari, Volume 7, Book 71, Number 582: Narrated Abu Huraira:*

"The Prophet (PBUH) said, "There is no disease that Allah has created, except that He also has created its treatment."

The next part of the paper will discuss the Islamic teachings and practices at different levels of disease prevention measures:

Primary prevention measures

A. Hygiene

Concerning Hand Hygiene: Islam emphasizes frequent hand washing to a mandatory of not less than five times a day before each obligatory prayer as illustrated in the following verse:

"O you who have believed, when you rise to [perform] prayer, wash your faces and your forearms to the elbows and wipe over your heads and wash your feet to the ankles. And if you are in a state of janabah, then purify yourselves. But if you are ill or on a journey or one of you comes from the place of relieving himself or you have contacted women and do not find water, then seek clean earth and wipe over your faces and hands with it. Allah does not intend to make difficulty for you, but He intends to purify you and complete His favor upon you that you may be grateful". (23)

Concerning Hand Washing: Narrated Salman al-Farsi: I read in the Torah that the blessing of food consists in ablution before it. So I mentioned it to the Prophet. He (SAW) said: The blessing of food consists in ablution before it and ablution (wash hands) after it. "Abu Dawud said: It is weak."

From the above Hadith and verse, all believers and Muslims are commanded to routinely wash the different parts of their body including the face, arms, and hands plus feet, among others. This is done to a minimum of not less than 5 times in a day for compulsory prayers in addition to other option (Sunnah Prayers).

If put in practice, the component of hand washing alone would play a crucial role in disease prevention through:

- i. Reducing germ transmission from the hands to various parts of body openings like the eyes the nose the mouth among others and cause illnesses.
- ii. Preventing faecal, oral and food borne diseases through contaminated hands that can contaminate foods and drinks including diarrheal diseases.

iii. Preventing the spread of respiratory tract infections including but not limited to flu, common colds, flu viruses, and other viruses including Corona Viruses disease 2019.

iv. Preventing and controlling Hospital acquired infections also known as Nosocomial infections among patients, care takers, and healthcare providers within a health care facility setting.

v. In a nutshell, frequent handwashing breaks the cycle of transmission and chain of disease transmission and infection thus making it hard for spread of diseases from one person.

B. Concerning Menstrual Hygiene cleanliness

Islam guides on handling of the menstruation periods as indicated in the following Quranic verse:

“They ask you ‘O Prophet’ about menstruation. Say, “Beware of its harm! So keep away, and do not have intercourse with your wives during their monthly cycles until they are purified. When they purify themselves, then you may approach them in the manner specified by Allah. Surely Allah loves those who always turn to Him in repentance and those who purify themselves.” (24)

Having sexual intercourse during menstruation has shown that there’s increased risk of infections particularly sexually transmitted diseases (STIs). Infections like HIV, Hepatitis B, Gonorrhoea, Chlamydia and others are blood borne and thus having sexual intercourse increases the chances of transmitting such infections.

During menstruation, the innate immune response within the vagina is distorted during menstruation because the usually acidic PH environment tends to neutral PH of blood among other factors.

All these changes contribute to the risks of spreading infections to both partners.

Therefore, this verse restraining men to stay away from their women during menstruation if put in practice, is a strong principle in the control of communicable diseases.

C.Oral hygiene

Concerning oral hygiene, it is reported in a hadith by Abu Hurairah (R.A) narrated that: Allah’s Messenger (P.B.U.H) said: "If it were not that it would be difficult on my nation, then I would have ordered them to use the

Siwak (tooth brushing) for each prayer.” Jami` at-Tirmidhi 22

Muslims pray five times a day, it thus follows that from this Hadith, that if it wasn’t to make it difficult for his people, the prophet peace be upon him would make it compulsory for Muslims to brush their teeth five times a day. This therefore remains (Sunnah) optional but desirable, if put into practice this principle can prevent oral infections and maintain oral hygiene.

D.Nutrition

(i) Moderation in eating: It is reported in a hadith that: On the authority of Al-Miqdaam ibn Maadiy-Karib who said: I heard the Messenger of Allah peace be upon saying: "No human ever filled a vessel worse than the **stomach**. Sufficient for any son of Adam are some morsels to keep his back straight. But if it must be, then one third for his food, one third for his drink and one third for his breath." Ahmad, At-Tirmidhi, An-Nasaa’I, Ibn Majah – Hadith sahih

(ii) Islam discourages excessive eating: as illustrated in following verses and Hadiths: O Children of Adam! wear your beautiful apparel at every time and place of prayer; eat and drink; But waste not by excess, for Allah loveth not the wasters. (25)

(iii) Nutrition...Emphasis on fruits and vegetables, Islam encourages eating balanced diet with emphasis on fruits and vegetables as illustrated in the following qur’anic verses and prophetic Hadiths;

(Every) fruit (enjoyment) will be there for them; they shall have whatever they call for; (26)

Ye shall have therein abundance of fruit, from which ye shall have satisfaction. (27)

And from the fruit of the date-palm and the vine, ye get out wholesome drink and food: behold, in this also is a sign for those who are wise. (28)

Fruits and vegetables are rich in minerals, fibers and antioxidants which support bodily functions through improving immunity and protecting the body against diseases in the following ways;

The presence of antioxidants and phytochemicals in fruits and vegetables reduce inflammation and also lowers the risk of chronic diseases including heart diseases, cancers diabetes, blood pressure, and obesity, among others.

E. Regarding Quarantine and control of outbreaks Its reported in a hadith that:

(i) Narrated Abu Huraira: Allah's Apostle said,“(There is) no 'Adwa (no contagious disease is conveyed without Allah's permission), nor is there any bad omen (from birds), nor is there any Hamah, nor is there any bad omen in the month of Safar, and one should run away from the leper as one runs away from a lion”*Sahih Bukhari, Volume 7, Book 71, Number 608:*

(ii) Umar & Allah's order; In one safar to Syam, there was outbreak of cholera and Umar R.A ordered Sahaabah to go back to Madinah. Abu 'Ubaida bin Al-Jarrah said (to 'Umar), "Are you running away from what Allah had ordained?" Umar said, "Would that someone else had said such a thing, O Abu 'Ubaida! Yes, we are running from what Allah has ordained, to what Allah has ordained.

(iii) Narrated: The Prophet said, "If you hear of an outbreak of plague in a land, do not enter it; but if the plague breaks out in a place while you are in it, do not leave that place. “*Sahih Bukhari Volume 7, Book 71, Number 624:*

The globe has witnessed the role and importance of quarantine in control of the spread epidemics during the recent COVID 19 outbreak.

This important principle of public health has been taught by prophet Muhamad Peace be upon him about 1400 years ago.

F. Unhealthy social practices prohibited. The almighty Allah says in the holy Quran in the following verses;

”They ask thee concerning wine and gambling. Say: "In them is great sin, and some profit, for men; but the sin is greater than the profit." They ask thee how much they are to spend; Say: "What is beyond your needs." Thus, doth Allah Make clear to you His Signs: In order that ye may consider. (29)

The Quran directly prohibits gambling, referring to it as an "abomination of Satan's handiwork" and a "grave sin". Specifically, Surah Al-Ma'idah (5:90-91) states that wine, gambling, idols, and divining arrows are evil and should be avoided to achieve success. (30)

From the above verses and principles, if put in practice, the following health benefits that are very crucial in

disease prevention health promotion and wellbeing can be achieved:

- (i) Avoiding alcohol reduces the risk of liver diseases such as cirrhosis and fatty liver disease.
 - (ii) Alcohol is a group 1 carcinogen (WHO classification) thus avoiding it reduces the risk of developing cancers like liver cancers, oesophageal cancers, breast cancers, colon cancers, among others.
 - (iii) Avoiding alcohol improves immune functionality as alcohol weakens it; this makes an individual susceptible to infections.
 - (iv) Alcohol is a **central nervous system depressant** and is linked to increased depression, anxiety, and even suicide thus avoiding it reduces the risk of mental health problems including depression and anxiety.
 - (v) Avoiding alcohol and other intoxicants prevents the risk of addiction and dependency with its associated risks.
 - (vi) Avoiding alcohol and other intoxicants minimizes the risks of road traffic accidents and domestic violence.
- Conclusively, it is very clear from the above verses that modern science and medicine strongly support the wisdom embedded in these verses, demonstrating the Quran's relevance to both **spiritual**, physical, and **public health**.

G. Mental and spiritual health: The holy quran says in the following quranic verses

Then will he be of those who believe, and enjoin patience, (constancy, and self-restraint), and enjoin deeds of kindness and compassion. (31)

This Qur'anic verse has significant public health implications. It emphasizes behavioural, social, and emotional traits that underpin many determinants of health. Below are key public health benefits derived from the teachings of this verse:

- i. Promotion of Mental and Emotional Well-being**
Patience, self-restraint, and constancy enhance emotional regulation, reduce stress, and build resilience. These qualities help lower rates of anxiety, depression, and interpersonal conflict, especially in communities facing hardship or trauma.
- ii. Encouragement of Altruism and Social Support**
Deeds of kindness and compassion nurture a culture of care and empathy. Social support networks improve outcomes in areas like chronic illness, maternal health, and mental well-being. Such values also contribute to lower violence and stronger communities.

iii. Behavior Change and Health Promotion

The verse encourages the promotion of virtuous behaviours like patience and compassion, aligning with public health approaches such as peer-to-peer health education and community mobilization. Modeling and advocating healthy behaviours is vital for disease prevention.

iv. Strengthening Community Resilience

In times of crisis (e.g., pandemics, disasters), communities practicing self-restraint, patience, and compassion show higher resilience. These traits support equity and cooperation, crucial for effective public health responses.

v. Reduction in Health Inequities

Compassionate behaviour encourages support for the vulnerable. This aligns with public health principles of social justice, helping ensure equitable access to healthcare and support for all individuals.

H. Sexual Hygiene: Concerning sexual hygiene and health

Nor come nigh to adultery: for it is a shameful (deed) and an evil, opening the road (to other evils). (32)

This verse forbids not only the act of adultery but even coming near it, emphasizing **prevention** — a principle that aligns closely with the goals of **public health, medicine, and scientific ethics**. Here's a breakdown of the **scientific, medical, and public health benefits** embedded in this divine command:

Scientific and Medical Benefits

i. Prevention of Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs).

Adultery and multiple sexual partners are strongly linked to higher risks of STIs including HIV/AIDS, syphilis, gonorrhoea, chlamydia, and HPV. Therefore, reducing illicit sexual contact directly contributes to lower transmission rates, protecting both the individual and the wider community.

ii. Protection of Reproductive Health.

Adultery can lead to unplanned pregnancies, often in contexts lacking proper medical care, leading to unsafe abortions or maternal complications. Reducing such behaviours supports maternal health, family planning, and better neonatal outcomes.

iii. Mental and Emotional Well-being.

Adultery often causes emotional distress, guilt, and relationship breakdowns, which are risk factors for anxiety, depression, and even suicidal ideation. Preserving marital fidelity strengthens psychological health and familial bonds.

Public Health Benefits

iv. Strengthening Family Structure

Stable families contribute to better child development, reduced domestic violence, and greater economic security. Children in stable households show better outcomes in education, mental health, and social behaviour.

v. Reducing Domestic and Gender-Based Violence

Adultery often leads to jealousy, distrust, and violence — sometimes fatal. A culture that respects marital boundaries reduces such conflict and promotes community safety.

vi. Promotion of Social Morality and Community Trust

Infidelity weakens social trust and breeds social unrest and disintegration of communities. Upholding chastity fosters social cohesion and mutual respect.

I. Mother & Child Health: Concerning mother and child health care the holy quran says:

Let the women live (in 'iddat) in the same style as ye live, according to your means: Annoy them not, so as to restrict them. And if they carry (life in their wombs), then spend (your substance) on them until they deliver their burden: and if they suckle your offspring), give them their recompense: and take mutual counsel together, according to what is just and reasonable. And if ye find yourselves in difficulties, let another woman suckle (the child) on the (father's) behalf. (33)

The following medical benefits can be derived from the above qur'anic verse.

i. Maternal Health Protection:

Requiring financial and emotional support for pregnant women after divorce ensures safe pregnancy and

delivery. Reduces risk of maternal mortality and complications, especially when women might otherwise be abandoned or lack access to care.

ii. Infant Health and Breastfeeding Support

The encouragement of breastfeeding and compensation for nursing mothers promotes:

Optimal infant nutrition

Strengthened immunity (through antibodies in breast milk)

Reduced risk of infections, malnutrition, and infant mortality.

If the biological mother cannot nurse, the verse promotes wet-nursing—an early form of alternative feeding aligned with today's donor milk or formula support.

iii. Economic and Psychosocial Support for Women.

Requiring men to financially support women during 'iddah and for nursing services reduces the risk of:

Poverty and malnutrition

Mental health decline (e.g., postpartum depression from stress or abandonment)

Homelessness or exploitation during a vulnerable period.

iv. Promotion of Shared Responsibility and Mutual Consultation

Encouraging "mutual counsel in justice and reason" fosters:

Co-parenting and conflict resolution; Reduced domestic stress; Protection of the child's psychosocial development through cooperative parenting.

v. Prevention of Abuse and Gender-Based Violence

The command "Annoy them not so as to restrict them" prevents emotional and economic abuse. It promotes dignity and rights for women, discouraging controlling behaviour that can lead to intimate partner violence (IPV).

vi. Value of exercise in maintaining health. The prophet peace be upon him advised, used to engage and also encouraged Muslims and also to teach their children to engage in the following exercises; Swimming, Archery and Horse riding. He used to walk at a fast pace; He ran races with his wife, Ayesha (Ra); He used to work with his hands whether athome, in the kitchen, or with his companions; collecting wood for fire.

Therefore, putting this prophetic Sunnah in practice is essential in preventing and minimizing the risks of non-communicable diseases like diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, heart diseases cancers, among others.

j. Mental and Spiritual Health: Stress is the most common root cause of mental and spiritual ailment of modern age.

Stress results from the following factors:

i. Fear of the unknown and trying to see through and control destiny.

ii. Losses in our life of people and things dear to us and our inability to recover those losses.

iii. Inner conflict between our heart and mind between what is known to be the truth and our failure to accept it as truth.

Let us examine how the Quran deals with such situations

Be sure we shall test you with something of fear and hunger, some loss in goods or lives or the fruits (of your toil) but give glad tidings to those who patiently persevere. (34)

Allah guides and warns us that mankind will be tested with trials but mankind is expected to persevere and exercise patience. The prophet peace be upon him guided man kind on what should be done in situation of Panic and Despair including the following:

i. Increase dhikr (Remembrance of God)

"Who have believed and whose heart have Rest in the remembrance of God. Verify in the remembrance of God, do hearts find rest. (35)

ii. Increase their prayer.

"O you who believe, seek help with steadfastness and prayer. For God is with those who are steadfast. (36)

iii. Ask forgiveness

"And I have said: seek forgiveness from your Lord. Lo He was ever forgiving."(37)

iv. The spiritual care involves the acts of worship

a. **Iman**-The essence of belief is to rid ourselves of all false Gods around us, or within us, and to worship no one except God alone.

b. **Salat:** There are three health aspects of Salat

Wadu: Washing all the exposed areas of the body, hand, feet, face, mouth, nostrils etc. 5 times a day is a healthy preventive procedure

Salaah

c. **Recitation of Quran:** Has a healing effect on body, mind, and heart. These healing effects are due to the effect of sound (Echo) and the meaning. The movement in Salaat are mild, uniform, and involve all muscles and joints.

d. **Fasting. Sawm:** The Islamic fasting: Islamic fasting is prescribed as

way training of our mind, and body in self-restraints.

"O you who believe is prescribed to you, as it was prescribed to those before you, so that you can learn self-restraint."

e. **zakat (Charity):** The word itself means purification and growth. Here it is meant to imply the purification of legitimately earned wealth.

Many of our crimes are committed with money or for love of money, and in the love of money one becomes violent in behaviour.

f. **Hajj (Pilgrimage to Mecca):** Few of the spiritual and health benefits are: Learn Prophet Ibrahim's submission and absolute surrender to God's will, the opportunity for repentance. The social and political gathering of the Ummah; Depicting brotherhood, and equality; Programming and testing us for physical endurance, a requirement for all able men and women.

Discussion:

Islam provides a robust ethical and practical framework for disease prevention and health promotion. By aligning modern health policies with religious principles, particularly Islamic practices, and teachings, we can enhance compliance, improve health outcomes, and foster holistic well-being. Medical professionals are urged to lead the way in merging these dual domains of science and faith for the benefit of individuals and societies.

The integration of Islamic values into public health strategies provides a culturally appropriate and spiritually enriching approach to disease prevention. While these teachings align well with scientific understanding, greater effort is needed to operation them within modern healthcare systems, by integrating the knowledge in the training of health care providers.

In Conclusion:

Islamic bodies including the Federation of Islamic Medical Associations (FIMA), the consortium of Islamic medical colleges (CIMCO), the Islamic universities, and colleges; the Muslim health professionals and communities have a unique responsibility to translate these teachings into practice through:

- Community-based health education that integrates Islamic values
- Advocacy against harmful cultural practices not aligned with Shariah
- Leveraging mosques and Islamic institutions as hubs for health promotion
- Mobilizing Muslim medical professionals to contextualize modern healthcare within Islamic frameworks.

Integration of Islamic knowledge and medical knowledge in training of Muslim health professionals, including development of training curriculums and emphasizing the use of the same in practice. (38)

Further investment should be put in scientific research studies to align the traditional prophetic medicine (Twibb a Nabbaw) with modern scientific medical knowledge. (38) More research should explore behavioural outcomes from faith-based health education programs and assess their effectiveness across populations. Muslims and the general community should be encouraged to put these Islamic principles and teachings in practice.

REFERENCES

1. COVID-19 deaths | WHO COVID-19 dashboard [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://data.who.int/dashboards/covid19/deaths>
2. COVID-19 cases | WHO COVID-19 dashboard [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://data.who.int/dashboards/covid19/cases>
3. Ndembi N, Folayan MO, Komakech A, Mercy K, Tessema S, Mbala-Kingebeni P, et al. Evolving Epidemiology of Mpox in Africa in 2024. *N Engl J Med* [Internet]. 2025 Jan 29 [cited 2025 May 29]; Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/39887004>
4. Monkey pox cumulative number of deaths globally as of April 2025 globally - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://www.google.com/search?q=Monkey+pox+cummulative+number+of+deaths+globally+as+of+April+2025>

https://www.google.com/search?q=globally&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=Monkey+pox+cummulative+number+of+deaths+globally+as+of+April+2025+globally&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCTQ0MTk3ajBqNKgCCLACAFEF1CNT7se9_ng&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

5. Pourrut X, Kumulungui B, Wittmann T, Moussavou G, Délicat A, Yaba P, et al. The natural history of Ebola virus in Africa. *Microbes Infect.* 2005;7(7–8):1005–14.

6. Ebola virus disease (EBV), Marburg, cholera, and other outbreaks have also hit the different parts of the world in the recent past - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: [https://www.google.com/search?q=Ebola+virus+disease+\(EBV\)%2C+Marburg%2C+cholera+and+other+outbreaks+have+also+hit+the+different+parts+of+the+world+in+the+recent+past&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=Ebola+virus+disease+\(EBV\)%2C+Marburg%2C+cholera+and+other+outbreaks+have+also+hit+the+different+parts+of+the+world+in+the+recent+past&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQIRiPAjIHCAIQIRiPAAtIBCDewNDVqMGo3qAIIIsAIB8QWQqTVkubhrIvEFkKk1ZLm4ayI&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=Ebola+virus+disease+(EBV)%2C+Marburg%2C+cholera+and+other+outbreaks+have+also+hit+the+different+parts+of+the+world+in+the+recent+past&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=Ebola+virus+disease+(EBV)%2C+Marburg%2C+cholera+and+other+outbreaks+have+also+hit+the+different+parts+of+the+world+in+the+recent+past&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQIRiPAjIHCAIQIRiPAAtIBCDewNDVqMGo3qAIIIsAIB8QWQqTVkubhrIvEFkKk1ZLm4ayI&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8)

7. Maham R, Bhatti OK, Öztürk AO. Impact of Islamic spirituality and Islamic social responsibility on employee happiness with perceived organizational justice as a mediator. *Cogent Business and Management.* 2020 Jan 1;7(1).

8. Islam is more than a religion—it is a comprehensive way and a complete system of life that encompasses guidance on spiritual, social, and physical well-being. - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: https://www.google.com/search?q=Islam+is+more+than+a+religion%E2%80%94it+is+a+comprehensive+way+and+a+complete+system+of+life+that+encompasses+guidance+on+spiritual%2C+social%2C+and+physical+well-being.&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=Islam+is+more+than+a+religion%E2%80%94it+is+a+comprehensive+way+and+a+complete+system+of+life+that+encompasses+guidance+on+spiritual%2C+social%2C+and+physical+well-being.&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOdIBCDYxNzlqMGo5qAIIIsAIB8QVvTokfZ8exhg&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

9. Islam: Is the total submission to the will of Allah; It is a complete way of life; and it is the best way of life. - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from:

https://www.google.com/search?q=Islam%3A+Is+the+total+submission+to+the+will+of+Allah%3B+It+is+a+complete+way+of+life%3B+and+it+is+the+best+way+of+life.&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=Islam%3A+Is+the+total+submission+to+the+will+of+Allah%3B+It+is+a+complete+way+of+life%3B+and+it+is+the+best+way+of+life.&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIHCAEQRRg60gEHNDU4ajBqN6gCCLACAFEFajJ-aDO-pLLxBWoyfmgzvqSy&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

10. Constitution of the World Health Organization [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/about/governance/constitution>

11. Mental Health Definition & Meaning | YourDictionary [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://www.yourdictionary.com/mental-health>

12. Mulemi BA. Spiritual Health. *Encyclopedia of Psychology and Religion* [Internet]. 2017 [cited 2025 May 29];1–5. Available from: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-27771-9_9222-1

13. definition of spiritual health - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: https://www.google.com/search?q=definition+of+spiritual+health&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=definition+of+spiritual+health&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyDwgAEEUYORiRAhiABBiKBTIHCAEQABiABDINCAIQABiRAhiABBiKBTIICAMQABgWGB4yCAgEEAAYFhgeMggIBRAAGBYHjIICAYQABgWGB4yCAgHEAAYFhgeMggICBAAGBYHjIICAKQABgWGB7SAQkxMTQ1OWowajmoAgiwAgHxBak3WO9qKPbT&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

14. Yousofi H. Human health and religious practices in Quraan. *Procedia Soc Behav Sci.* 2011;30:2487–90.

15. McCarthy EF. Genetic diseases of bones and joints. *Semin Diagn Pathol.* 2011 Feb;28(1):26–36.

16. A disease, is any harmful deviation from the normal structural or functional state of an organism, generally associated with certain signs and symptoms and differing in nature from physical injury. A diseased organism commonly exhibits signs or symptoms indicative of its abnormal state - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://www.google.com/search?q=A+disease%2C+is+an+y+harmful+deviation+from+the+normal+structural+or+f>

[unctional+state+of+an+organism%2C+generally+associated+with+certain+signs+and+symptoms+and+differing+in+nature+from+physical+injury.+A+diseased+organism+commonly+exhibits+signs+or+symptoms+indicative+of+its+abnormal+state&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=A+disease%2C+is+any+harmful+deviation+from+the+normal+structural+or+functional+state+of+an+organism%2C+generally+associated+with+certain+signs+and+symptoms+and+differing+in+nature+from+physical+injury.+A+diseased+organism+commonly+exhibits+signs+or+symptoms+indicative+of+its+abnormal+state&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQABgNGIAEMggIAhAAGBYHjIICAMQABgWGB4yDQgEEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyDQgFEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyCggEEAA YgAQYogTSAQkxOTc3N2owajeoAgCwAgA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8](https://www.google.com/search?q=communicable+diseases+definition+WHO&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=communicable+diseases+definition+WHO&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQABgNGIAEMggIAhAAGBYHjIICAMQABgWGB4yDQgEEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyDQgFEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyCggEEAA YgAQYogTSAQkxOTc3N2owajeoAgCwAgA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8)

17. communicable diseases definition WHO - Google Search [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: https://www.google.com/search?q=communicable+diseases+definition+WHO&rlz=1C1GCEU_enUG1161UG1163&oq=communicable+diseases+definition+WHO&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIJCAEQABgNGIAEMggIAhAAGBYHjIICAMQABgWGB4yDQgEEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyDQgFEAA YhgMYgAQYigUyCggEEAA YgAQYogTSAQkxOTc3N2owajeoAgCwAgA&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8

18. Noncommunicable diseases [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>

19. Newman M. Research Guides: Islamic Law: Primary Sources of Islamic Law. [cited 2025 May 29]; Available from: <https://guides.law.columbia.edu/c.php?g=1221841&p=9280464>

20. Primary Sources of Islamic Law - Islamic Law - Research Guides at Columbia Law School [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 3]. Available from: <https://guides.law.columbia.edu/c.php?g=1221841&p=9280464>

21. Newman M. Research Guides: Islamic Law: Secondary Sources of Islamic Law. [cited 2025 May 29]; Available from: <https://guides.law.columbia.edu/c.php?g=1221841&p=9280607>

22. Secondary Sources of Islamic Law - Islamic Law - Research Guides at Columbia Law School [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://guides.law.columbia.edu/c.php?g=1221841&p=9280607>

23. Surah Ma'idah Ayat 6 (5:6 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 4]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-maidah/ayat-6/>

24. Surah Al-Baqarah Ayat 222 (2:222 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 6]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-baqarah/ayat-222/>

25. Surah Al-A'raf Ayat 31 (7:31 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 29]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-al-araf/ayat-31/>

26. Surah Yaseen Ayat 57 (36:57 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 4]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-yaseen/ayat-57/>

27. Surah Zukhruf Ayat 73 (43:73 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-zukhruf/ayat-73/>

28. Surah An-Nahl Ayat 67 (16:67 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 4]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-nahl/ayat-67/>

29. Surah Al-Baqarah Ayat 219 (2:219 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 4]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-baqarah/ayat-219/>

30. Surah Ma'idah Ayat 90 (5:90 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-maidah/ayat-90/>

31. Surah Balad Ayat 17 (90:17 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-al-balad/ayat-17/>

32. Surah Al-Isra Ayat 32 (17:32 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 6]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-isra/ayat-32/>

33. Surah Talaq Ayat 6 (65:6 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 6]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-at-talaaq/ayat-6/>

34. Surah Al-Baqarah Ayat 155 (2:155 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-baqarah/ayat-155/>

35. Surah Ar-Ra'd Ayat 28 (13:28 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-rad/ayat-28/>

36. Surah Al-Baqarah Ayat 153 (2:153 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-baqarah/ayat-153/>

37. Surah Nuh Ayat 10 (71:10 Quran) With Tafsir - My Islam [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 30]. Available from: <https://myislam.org/surah-nuh/ayat-10/>

38. Rashid N. Prophetic Medicine (Twibb Nabawi) Principles in Clinical Practice: Experiences From Uganda. International Journal of Human and Health Sciences (IJHHS) [Internet]. 2024 Aug 25 [cited 2025 May 30];8(3):241–8. Available from: <https://ijhhsfimaweb.info/index.php/IJHHS/article/view/718>

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